
EFFECTIVENESS OF APPLYING METHODS OF TEACHING FOOTBALL ELEMENTS TO CHILDREN AND DYNAMICS OF OBTAINED RESULTS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7859601>

Barno Pulatovna Abdullaeva

babdullayeva44@gmail.com

Angren University, senior teacher of the department of " Pedagogy and Psychology"

Abstract.

The article discusses the effectiveness of teaching the first elements of football to students of educational institutions in the pre-school education system and the development of effective methods for this. The increase in the requirements for preparing a child for school has led to a decrease in physical activity due to the increase in hours allocated for intellectual development. In order to solve these problems, the article discusses new methods for organizing active physical activity of children from preschool age.

Key words.

motor activity, exercises, ball, ball exercises, preschool education, child's body, coordination ability, football elements, physical qualities.

The application of the developed physical training method to the children of the senior and preparatory group , based on the use of football elements, had a positive effect on the children's physical fitness. After the pedagogical experiment, the boys and girls of the experimental group showed significantly higher results than the children of the control group in all control exercises (p 0.05).

According to the results of the development of coordination during the experiment, the experimental group showed the greatest increase in indicators in the tests that determine the development of static and dynamic balance. At the end of the experiment, the results that determine the qualities of agility movement recovery exceeded the indicators of children in the control group. The results of the development of all coordination skills of the children of the experimental and control groups have statistically significant differences.

During the pedagogical experiment, no significant differences were found in the data obtained for physical development in the control and experimental groups. This shows that the growth of anthropometric indicators in both groups is related to the process of natural development and the influence of physical education. It

was found that the training had a positive effect on the functional system of the children of the experimental group.

Studying the level of mental development of children during the pedagogical experiment allowed us to determine that after the end of the experiment, the number of children in the experimental group with highly developed mental processes significantly increased compared to the number of children in the control group. In the experimental group, a positive indicator of interpersonal relations in the group and relations with parents was found, as well as an increase in emotional state and interest in physical education classes. A positive indicator was not detected in the control group.

In the experimental group, the use of experimental methods based on the use of football elements in physical education training made it possible to increase the level of development of the movement skills of the foot with the ball. At the end of the experiment, the control group used methods of dribbling movements, which allowed to carry out the movement of the ball with minimal time.

The accuracy of hitting the target with the ball by the children of the experimental group shows that the diversity of the hitting methods, the technique of execution and the results increase in accuracy. Such an increase in movement skills was achieved by correctly using the possibilities of the anatomical structure of various joints.

At the end of the pedagogical experiment, it is evidenced that the children of the control and experimental groups analyzed the performance of movement activities in order to more effectively perform the methods of performing strokes. In the test task, "10 m round the poles with a ball", the focus was not on the way the children performed the task, but on completing it in the minimum time. Performing movements is a confirmation of the transition from activity to movement skills.

Thus, the obtained data confirm the effectiveness of physical education methods based on the use of football elements in children of senior and preparatory groups in a preschool educational organization.

Conclusions

Research analysis shows that the use of elements of sports games in the course of physical education and wellness activities in preschool educational organizations has a positive effect on increasing the level of physical fitness, physical and mental development of preschool children. At the same time, in the theory of physical education, the problem of the use of football elements in the physical training of

large and preparatory groups of preschool educational organizations is little studied and not based on experience.

Based on the analysis of the questionnaire data, it was determined that the percentage of the use of sports games in the system of physical education for children of senior and preparatory groups in preschool educational organizations is from 10% to 15% of the number of exercises recommended in the general program. In various forms of physical exercise, experts use elements of basketball (100%), volleyball (27%) and only 13% of football. Experts emphasize the need to develop training methods (87%), to combine movement and cognitive activity, to develop coordination and to expand the experience of children's movement activities by creating conditions for performing new movement activities with legs that correspond to children's age characteristics (79%).

Ball possession characteristics of senior and preschool children are revealed, describing ambiguous movement characteristics in solving soccer movement problems. The majority of boys (57.1%) and girls (46.2%) dribble the ball with their right foot only, 14-23% of children dribble only with their left foot. Carrying the ball with the right and left foot is used by only 30% of boys and girls. In children, dribbling is done with the inner part of the foot or with the joint of the tip of the foot and the inner part of the foot, which makes it difficult to accelerate forward. Most children kick the ball with their toes (86.3%). Other kicking methods are not practiced by children, which indicates a low level of control of the movement and a limitation of the full range of leg movements at the hip, knee and calf joints.

The methodology of physical training is developed for children of senior and preparatory groups based on the use of football elements, and it is based on the following: selection of available methods and techniques for kicking and kicking according to the age characteristics of children: carrying the ball, passing the ball, stopping and performing other actions selection of exercises that ensure coordination for: distribution of exercises according to the complexity of execution, creation of special blocks of exercises for mastering motor activities and games in the conditions of combining children's movement and cognitive activity . The teaching methodology is 25-30 minutes per week during physical education in a traditional preschool educational institution, 25% (in 34 lessons), 50% (in 44 lessons) and 100% (in 24 lessons) of the total training time compared to other means. elements are used.

It was found that physical education activities based on the use of football elements have a positive effect on the development of physical qualities of children

of senior and preparatory groups. At the end of the educational experiment, the children of the experimental group showed significantly higher results than their peers in the control group ($p < 0.05$): "Running 10 m from the movement", "30 m running", "Running along the snake track", "Shuttle running 6x5 m", "Standing long jump", "Bending forward", "Lifting the trunk". A similar situation was used to compare the results of the tests describing the level of development of coordination ability: "Stork in the swamp", "Running to the ball with visual and auditory cues" and "Shuttle running with lifting equipment" ($p < 0.05$).

After the end of the pedagogical experiment, the improvement of the results in the test of moving the ball between the posts for a distance of 10 m in the children of the experimental group is significantly higher in both boys (45.7%) and girls (50.5%) than in the control group, which is reasonable for solving the movement task using methods - achieved by dribbling the ball with the inside and outside of the foot. The effectiveness of the methodology is also confirmed by the results of the "Kick the ball at 4 goals" test. At the end of the educational experiments, the accuracy of the shots and the time of execution of the children of the experimental group are much higher than those of the control group. Children in the experimental group hit the target on average 28% higher and made 85.2% of the total number of hits for boys and 80.7% for girls. In the control group, the effectiveness of boys was 60.2 %, and for girls - 53.6% ($p < 0.05$).

The effectiveness of the experimental method is confirmed by the results of physical development of preschool children. At the end of the pedagogical experiment, the ratio of the physical development of the children in the experimental group was 32% higher than in the control group ($p < 0.05$), which is the result of the increase in the intensity and size of the children's movement activity during the process of playing football.

The analysis of the effect of the experimental method on the mental development of 5-7-year-old children shows that the level of mental development of children of the experimental group - logical thinking, short-term memory, imagination and voluntary attention - is significantly higher than that of the control group. At the end of the pedagogical experiment, the number of children with highly developed mental processes was 41.3% in the experimental group and 18.1% in the control group. The positive dynamics of the results in the "No Animal" and "Family Picture" tests showed that the relationship between the children in the group and their parents improved during the pedagogical experience. The number of children in the experimental group with high peer relations increased by an

average of 50%, and in the control group by 9.1%. 40.9% of children in the experimental group had positive relationships in the family, which is much higher than in the control group.

REFERENCES:

1. Kerimov F.A. Scientific studies in the field of sports. study guide. Tashkent 2004. 334 p.
2. Olimov M.S., Shakirjanova K.T., Rafiyev H.T., Tokhtaboyev N.T., Smuriygina L.V. and others. / Textbook. Theory and methodology of athletics. / - Tashkent, 2018.
3. Olimov M.S., Soliyev I.R., Haydarov B.Sh. / Textbook. Improving sports pedagogical skills. - Tashkent.: 2017 .
4. Abdullaeva B.P., Using information and communication technologies in teaching process of various primary school subjects. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, 8 (10), 67-70. Progressive Academic Publishing, UK www.idpublications.org 14.10.2020
5. Abdullaeva B.P., Methodology of organizing football lessons in a preschool educational institution Bosma Academic research in educational sciences, Issue 3, 2020, pp 777-783.
6. Abdullaeva B.P., Organization and methodology of conducting football lessons in a preschool institution. Bosma ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal <https://saarj.com> ISSN: 2249-7137 Vol. 11, Issue 1, January 2021 Impact Factor:
7. Abdullaeva B.P., Organization of physical training in preschool educational organizations and primary classes Bosma ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 3 | 2021 ISSN: 2181-1385 Scientific Journal Impact Factor (SJIF) 2021: 5.723
8. Abdullaeva B.P., Teaching A Child To Play Football From A Youth The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research (ISSN-2642-7478) Published: April 30, 2021 Pages: 147- 151
9. Abdullaeva B.P., Football as a means of physical education CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS - 2767-3278 02-08-16 Accepted 26th August, 2021 Analysis of the Level of Proficiency in the Elements of Playing Football by children of senior preschool age
10. B.P. Abdullaeva Characteristics of Using Football Elements in the Physical Education of Preschool Children Global Scientific Review 10, 46-51 .